

Cross-generational analysis of predictive factors of addictive behavior in smartphone usage

Abstract

Smartphone addiction has been widely researched in recent years, and the effects of various demographic, personality-linked, psychological, and emotional variables, have been found. Our research goal was to examine this phenomenon from the cross-generational perspective and compare the factors that can predict smartphone addiction for different age groups. We conducted a study with 216 Israeli smartphone users, representing three generations of smartphone users: Generation X, Generation Y, and Generation Z, who filled in an 80-item questionnaire. The factors examined included the social environment pressure to use smartphone, emotional gain from smartphones, personality, daily usage time, various mobile apps and user needs. The main finding of the study is that a significantly higher level of addictive behavior was found for Generation Y compared to the other two generations. The strongest predictive factors in the computed hierarchical regression model for all three generations were social environment pressure and emotional gain. Interestingly, emotional gain from smartphone use, which reflects users' enjoyment and positive emotions along with relief of negative emotions and psychological states, was significantly higher for generation Z than for the older generations. In addition, neuroticism and the daily usage time appeared as predictive factors for the younger generations, and for Generation Z alone the WhatsApp app usage was found as a significant predictive factor as well. This study contributes to understanding the factors of smartphone addictive behavior for different generations, which might lead to more effective educational measures and explanatory campaigns on technology effects on psychological well-being.

Keywords: smartphone addictive behavior, smartphone addiction, cross-generation analysis, behavioral addiction, predictive factors, smartphone addictive behavior scale

1. Introduction

In the age of Internet and communication technology, people are becoming increasingly technology-dependent in various aspects of their lives and daily functioning, and smartphones are the spearhead of this process. This change has brought the Internet to every place through various ubiquitous devices including smartphones, and allowed them a more central role in their users' lives than in the past. In Israel, by the end of 2013, 57% of the population owned a smartphone (Google's Our Mobile Planet survey), positioning it in twelfth place worldwide and outranking the USA and most European countries. The first studies about smartphones entering our lives show that they can be in use for 2.5

hours a day, or even more (Oulasvirta, Rattenbury, Ma, & Raita, 2012; van Deursen, Bolle, Hegner, & Kommers, 2015). However, alongside the advantages of availability of information and communications, research shows that such technology also has a negative effect on user behavior and functioning, and on the mental and physical health of both the individual and the entire society (Lanaj, Johnson, & Barnes, 2014).

Young (1998) and later Young & Abreu (2011) defined Internet addiction as an impulse-control disorder, where an individual loses control of the excessive Internet use even when it negatively affects his/her life. Similarly, past research categorized problematic or addictive use of smartphones as behavioral addictions (Shaffer, 1996; van Deursen et al., 2015), expressed in the inability to limit the smartphone use despite its destructive effects on the user's functioning. The previous studies on behavioral addictions laid the foundation for the importance of studying this phenomenon. These studies examined gambling and computer game addiction (Parker, Taylor, Eastabrook, Schell, & Wood, 2008; Shaffer, 1996), problematic Internet use and Internet addiction (Billieux & Van der Linden, 2012; Chou & Hsiao, 2000; Frangos, Frangos, & Kiohos, 2010; LaRose, Lin, & Eastin, 2003; Li & Chung, 2006; Weinstein & Lejoyeux, 2010; Whang, Lee, & Chang, 2003; Young, 1999; Yu, Kim, & Hay, 2013), problematic use and addiction to mobile phones (Beranuy, Oberst, Carbonell, & Chamarro, 2009; Bianchi & Phillips, 2005; Carbonell, Oberst, & Beranuy, 2013; Jenaro, Flores, Gamez-Vela, Gonzaleiz-Gil, & Caballo, 2007), and recently also smartphone addiction (Kwon et al., 2013; Lee, Chang, Lin & Cheng, 2014; Lopez-Fernandez, Honrubia-Serrano, Freixa-Blanxart, & Gibson, 2014; Oulasvirta et al., 2012; van Deursen et al., 2015).

The Internet and smartphones share similar characteristics, and, therefore, scales have been developed to assess smartphone addiction levels based on existing Internet addiction scales (Kwon et al., 2013). However, there are also unique features of smartphones, such as technological triggers (sound notifications), a variety of mobile apps, and having the smartphone at all times in every place, which are likely to contribute to the development of smartphone addiction (Oulasvirta et al., 2012; van Deursen et al., 2015). The negative effects of the behavioral addictions are distress and lack of functioning (Aboujaoude, Koran, Gamel, Large, & Serpe, 2006), tiredness and lack of concentration, physical, psychological, economic, and social problems (Young, 1999), and harm to the work-life balance (Oulasvirta et al., 2012). These effects are also likely to appear in the case of smartphone addiction (Lanaj et al., 2014), increasing the importance of researching and understanding the phenomenon and its causes.

The factors found to contribute to smartphone addiction were various demographic parameters, such as gender, age, profession, level of education (Kwon et al., 2013; van Deursen et al., 2015), personality parameters, such as neuroticism and extroversion (Pearson & Hussein, 2015), and poor self-regulation (van Deursen et al., 2015). In addition, psychological and emotional states were found to correlate with smartphone addiction, such as loneliness (Amichai-Hamburger, Wainapel, & Fox, 2002; Park & Lee, 2014), stress (Chiu, 2014; Lee et al., 2014; Samaha & Haw, 2016; Sapacz, Rockman, & Clark, 2016), and emotional gains derived mainly from using social media and games (Jeong, Kim, Yum, & Hwang, 2016; Salehan & Negahban, 2013), in accordance with the content and process gratifications theory (Song, LaRose, Eastin, & Lin, 2004).

Previous studies demonstrate significant cross-generational differences in the use of new technologies (Charness & Bosman, 1992; Lenhart, Purcell, Smith, & Zickuhr, 2010), as well as in personality traits and emotional and social states (Clarke, 2006; Howe & Strauss, 2004). Therefore, the different generations may demonstrate different behavior in regard to smartphone problematic use and addictive behavior. However, most of the smartphone addiction research above was based on a single generation as a sample population.

1.1 Habitual use and addiction to media and Internet

Theories and methodologies of media and Internet addiction provide basis for the smartphone addiction research. The theoretical model for media addiction describes such behavior as a process that leads to shaping habits and pathology (LaRose et al., 2003). The stages of the model are as follows:

- Occupying the mind: excessive use that is expressed when the user experiences a desire to use media, modifies other activities to accommodate media use, or experiences tension or excitement when using media.
- Progression: the use needs to occur in increasingly larger “units” every time media is consumed, so as to achieve the same effect.
- Deterioration: the user makes repeated attempts to control the activity, but fails.
- Regression syndrome: when the activity is unavailable to the user, s/he experiences panic, anxiety, disquiet, or other negative effects.
- Losing control: the user is involved in the activity for longer than planned, or feels that the use is no longer in his control and cannot be halted.
- Consequences for the environment: less time allocated to other activities, losing interest in them, and ignoring the disruptions caused as a result, such as dealing with monetary, familial, or employment issues.

- Concealment: the user tries to hide how much time he spends on media or his involvement in it, from others.
- Escapism: the activity is seen as a means of escape or as something that neutralizes or moderates bad moods.

Another theory explains the sources for addiction or dependency on media and its development among individuals with a tendency to addiction or personality disorders. Smith (1986) argues that television addiction can possibly be the result of an individual's defective autonomous ego. McIlwraith (1998) estimates that an addictive personality suffers from basic personality traits which increase the tendency to addictive behavior, such as, a neurotic need, searching for excitement, or a lack of imagination.

The literature differentiates between media and technology addiction, termed behavioral addictions, and physiological addictions (Greenberg, Lewis, & Dodd, 1999; Griffiths & Hunt, 1998; Shaffer, 1996). These studies discovered low to moderate correlations among "behavioral" addicts addicted to video games, television, and Internet, and "physiological" addicts addicted to drugs and alcohol. In contrast, they found significant statistical correlations between addiction to television consumption and personality traits. However, Finn (1992) found that physiological addictions to marijuana and alcohol had an inverse correlation to television consumption, and that they, therefore, cannot reflect the same basic personality syndrome. Moreover, the correlation between addictions can be a result of a shared lifestyle or cultural or demographic factors that encourage addictions in various behavioral areas, and not because of someone's personality (Rozin & Stoess, 1993). There is also a correlation with other personality types, such as a depressive personality and low self-confidence that can be a result of addiction, or, alternatively, its cause (Marlatt, Baer, Donovan, & Kivlahan, 1988).

Based on the above theories, Young (1998) developed a scale for examining Internet addiction and suggested ways of treating it. At a later stage, this scale served as the basis for development of scales for smartphone addiction (Kwon et al., 2013). Internet addiction has been defined as a behavioral addiction (Whang, Lee, & Chang, 2003). However, there is no consensus in the literature regarding pathological and compulsive nature of excessive Internet use (Kardefelt-Winther, 2014). Therefore, this behavior was alternatively defined as problematic use emanating from habit and a wish to reduce negative emotions and escape from reality (Huisman, Garretsen, & Van Den Eijnden, 2000; Kardefelt-Winther, 2014). Social pressure, low emotional intelligence, and poor self-control ability were found to be significant factors in problematic Internet use (Beranuy et al., 2009; LaRose et al., 2003; Parker et al., 2008) and Internet addiction (Kwon et al., 2013). Likewise, social and hedonic Internet use that reinforces and helps escapism from reality increases the risk of Internet addiction (Chou & Hsiao, 2000; Li & Chung, 2006; Yang & Tung, 2007). Various studies show that there are gender difference

in the level of problematic Internet use (Billieux & Van der Linden, 2012) and Internet addiction (Frangos et al., 2010), and that men have a greater tendency to Internet overuse (Choi et al., 2009), since they have lower emotional awareness and use Internet more hedonically than women.

1.2 Mobile phone habitual use, problematic use and addiction

Another example of behavioral addiction is addiction to mobile phones that allow making calls and sending text messages in every place and time, in addition to surfing the web (Hong, Chiu, and Huang, 2013). In some studies this phenomenon was considered a problematic mobile phone use (Bianchi and Phillips, 2005; Billieux et al., 2015) or habitual behavior (Oulasvirta et al., 2012), rather than pathological behavior and addiction. Bianchi and Phillips (2005) suggested a scale for estimating problematic mobile phone use (PMPU). The scale is based on existing scales in the literature, that measure a tendency to drug and alcohol addiction. They found that being extrovert, having low self-esteem, and being young, increase the tendency for problematic use in situations where mobile phone use is illegal and dangerous, such as, while driving. However, no correlation was found between neuroticism and problematic mobile phone use. Other studies that used the PMPU scale (Öztunç, 2013; Tan, Pamuk, & Dönder, 2013) questioned hundreds of students in Turkey, and found a significant correlation between loneliness, shyness, and length of time in use and addiction to mobile phones. Likewise, the latter study discovered higher PMPU for male students than female ones. Another measure, the Mobile Phone Addiction Scale (MPAS), was developed by Hong, Chiu, and Huang (2013), based on Young's scale (1998) for mobile phone addiction. The scale included three groups of questions that examine the negative effect of mobile phones, including time management problems, study problems, and escape from reality. As a result of a survey of over 200 female Taiwanese students, the researchers discovered that being socially extrovert and stressed increased the risks for mobile phone addiction.

Smartphones are the current ultimate in the evolution of mobile phones, and in addition to calls and text messages they include features that did not exist in the first mobile phones, such as various mobile apps (social, entertainment, and informative), ease of Internet surfing and improved user interfaces. These features can indirectly lead to an increase in the risks of smartphone habitual use, problematic use and addiction. An experiment that examined habits which lead to increased smartphone use (Oulasvirta et al., 2012) discovered a new habit that researchers coined "the checking habit": a brief, repetitive checking of the dynamic content accessible on the device, and the information it provides, serving as "reinforcement" to the user. Such habits, triggered by the technology of sound notifications, have the potential to develop smartphone addictive behavior. In our study, we defined this checking need triggered by notifications, as a technology-triggered need, and examined if it has a correlation to the extent of the subjects' addictive behavior. We hypothesize that:

H1: Technology-triggered need is positively related to smartphone addictive behavior.

1.3 Factors of smartphone addictive behavior

1.3.1 Social environment pressure

A study that examined the differences between owners of smartphones and of traditional mobile devices (Lee, Chang, Cheng, & Lin, 2016) found that smartphone owners experience greater stress than those who own traditional mobile devices. Other studies found that various kinds of stress and social anxiety are a significant factor in smartphone addiction (Chiu, 2014; Lee, Chang, Lin, & Cheng, 2014; Samaha & Hawi, 2016; Sapacz et al., 2016; van Deursen et al., 2015). In light of these findings, we decided to examine the relationship between social-environmental pressure and the tendency towards smartphone addiction. But, as opposed to previous studies, we considered the direct social pressure to use smartphones. In particular, we examined whether smartphone use by those in the subject's vicinity leads the subject to do the same even without a concrete reason to do so. We hypothesize that:

H2: Social environment pressure to smartphone use by those in the subject's vicinity is positively related to the subject's addictive behavior.

1.3.2 Social and entertainment application use

One of the smartphone's most addictive features is social networking (Salehan & Negahban, 2013). Salehan & Negahban (2013) discovered that the use of social networking apps among young people in the USA is a significant predictor for addiction to mobile devices. Their results also demonstrated that the use of mobile social apps is influenced by both the size of the social network and the user's social intensity. A study that was carried out on Korean students (Park & Lee, 2014) also reported that addicted users have a clear preference for social networking sites (SNSs). A diary study of smartphone use (Oulasvirta et al., 2012) examined how respondents described their experience of repeated use of their device, and found that only a small proportion of the participants were aware of their repeated phone usage. The most common motivation was that the mobile phone provides accessibility, and the primary motives for habits were entertainment and "killing time". Awareness of the usage itself and problems of repeated use were the most underestimated and only a small percentage noted them. The few respondents who did refer to repeated use used expressions like "annoying", "too much of a temptation", "a trap", "an activity that distracts me from other activities", and "addiction" when talking about Facebook. Another study, carried out on 386 respondents in Netherlands (van Deursen et al., 2015), reported social smartphone use as one of the factors increasing the risk of smartphone addiction. In light of the above findings in our study, we are examining correlation and effect between the amount of usage of a broad range of mobile apps (social, entertainment – such as games, and

informative apps) and between the user's different needs, and the extent of smartphone addiction. We investigate the following research question:

R1: Are various mobile apps and users' needs related to smartphone addictive behavior?

1.3.3 Emotional gain

The various smartphone uses serve as a "reward" and social and content gratifications (Song, LaRose, Eastin, & Lin, 2004; Yang & Tung, 2007). Moreover, following Kardefelt-Winther's (2014) motivational theory for compensative Internet use, excessive smartphone use might also compensate for different emotional and psychological problems, such as stress, loneliness and depression, and increase the sense of enjoyment and security. Therefore, in this study we have developed a scale for the emotional factor that is related to smartphone addictive behavior, reflecting these emotional gains.

We hypothesize that:

H3: Emotional gain is positively related to smartphone addictive behavior.

1.3.4 Personality traits

Various personality and demographic parameters that were found to have an effect on Internet and traditional mobile phone addiction were also examined in the context of smartphone addiction. Thus, van Deursen et al. (2015) discovered that poor self-control (self-regulation) causes smartphone addiction. High narcissism and neuroticism levels were found to be predictors of a tendency to smartphone addiction (Pearson & Hussein, 2015). The respondents with a high tendency to addiction have a high tendency to shyness, loneliness, depression and low self-esteem (Park & Lee, 2014). In addition, a large-scale study in Taiwan discovered that various personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism) were found to be significantly linked to addiction to social networks, such as Facebook (Tang, Chen, Yang, Chung, & Lee, 2016). These personality characteristics are liable to also lead to smartphone addiction, since social network use on smartphones is one of the significant causes of addiction, as the above studies demonstrate. Therefore, in the current study we examine the personality as a factor related to smartphone addictive behavior, by adopting the full Big Five questionnaire (McCrae & John, 1992). We explore the following research question:

R2: Are Big Five personality traits related to smartphone addictive behavior?

1.3.5 Demographic variables

Demographic variables such as work, education (Kwon et al., 2013) and gender (Lee, Chang, Lin, & Cheng, 2014; Park & Lee, 2014; van Deursen et al., 2015) were discovered to affect tendency to

smartphone addiction. We also examined the relationship between gender and the extent of smartphone addiction. We hypothesize that:

H4: Women are likely to exhibit a higher smartphone addictive behavior than men in our sample.

1.3.6 Analysis of cross-generational differences in smartphone addictive behavior

Most of the aforementioned studies focus on young users and college students from Generation Y. Reference to the age of the smartphone users appeared in the study by van Deursen et al. (2015), who discovered a negative correlation between age and tendency to develop problematic smartphone habits and addiction. In this study, we have extended the examination of the effect of age, and examined the cross-generational differences in the context of smartphone addictive behavior. In particular, we also examine separately which reasons and factors were dominant for each generation. We have adopted the SAS scale (Kwon et al., 2013) after its translation into Hebrew, and it being condensed by removing the questions that were not directly connected to the user's behavior as described in detail in the next chapter. We used this scale to measure to what extent smartphone addictive behavior exists among the population of users in Israel using the entire sample, and for each generation separately. We propose the following hypotheses:

H5a: Generation X is likely to show a lower level of smartphone addictive behavior than generations Y and Z.

H5b: Generation Y is likely to show a lower level of smartphone addictive behavior than generation Z.

H5c: Generation X is likely to experience a lower level of social environment pressure to use smartphones than generation Y, and generation Y is likely to experience a lower level of social environment pressure to use smartphones, than generation Z.

H5d: Generation Z is likely to show a higher level of social application use via smartphones, than generation Y, while generation Y is likely to show a higher level of social application use via smartphones, than generation X.

Therefore, the primary research goal of this study was to systematically examine the cross-generational differences in the extent of smartphone addictive behavior, and analyze the related factors of this phenomenon for each generation separately. To this end, we have defined a short and focused scale for measuring smartphone addictive behavior, based on Kwon et al.'s (2013) Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS). Unlike SAS, the new scale includes questions that assess only behavioral aspects of smartphone use, indicating excessive use, inability to limit usage, and negative effects of that usage on the user's life. Conversely, aspects that serve as emotional and social reinforcement were removed from the measure of addictive behavior, and included in the factor scales to measure the emotional and social-environmental factors. This is since they do not reflect actual behavior, but rather the factors that might be related to the user's behavior and lead to addiction.

In addition, we expanded the spectrum of the potential factors and added smartphone information consumption behavior as part of the process and social usage factors (van Deursen et al., 2015). Thus, we examined the extent of the relationship of various mobile apps (social, informative, and entertainment), as well as that of different user needs (need for information, for a virtual community, emotional needs), on the extent of user smartphone addictive behavior.

This study's expected contribution is understanding and a more in-depth investigation of smartphone addictive behavior in the cross-generational context, which consequences might affect millions of users. The results of the study have practical implications for e-commerce, education and public well-being.

2. Method

2.1. Study Population

The study population comprised 216 respondents in Israel. We filtered out four subjects who reported that they do not own a smartphone. Two more subjects' responses were removed since they have not answered all of the items in the questionnaire. Thus, the final sample used in the analysis of this study comprised 209 subjects.

The distribution of the study's demographic variables is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the sample (N=209).

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>	<i>N</i>	
Gender	Male	37%	78
	Female	63%	128
Age	Generation Z: ages 13-19	34%	71
	Generation Y: ages 20-35	43%	90
	Generation X: ages 36-68	23%	48

2.2. Research variables and validation method

To assess the validity of the hypotheses, we created an 80-item questionnaire that examines smartphone addictive behavior and its potential factors of influence.

The questionnaire was divided into the following six groups of questions:

1. The first group included demographic data such as year of birth, gender, how many years a user has been using a smartphone, how much time a user spent daily lately using the smartphone (items 1-4 on the questionnaire). The two latter items were added, since we anticipated that habitual and addictive behavior might take time to develop and could be increased over time. Thus, the longer a user has been using a smartphone and the more time s/he spends using it daily, the higher his/her addictive behavior.
2. The second group is an addiction questionnaire that was built based on SAS validated on a total of 197 Korean participants with Cronbach's $\alpha=0.967$ (Kwon et al., 2015), but in its short 18-question version, that included questions that only reflect behavioral aspects, and is based on questions 1-9, 19, 21-24, 29, 40, 43-47 in the original SAS questionnaire (these are items 5-22 in our questionnaire). For example, “When I go to sleep, my smartphone is usually next to me,” “I am busy with my smartphone for more time than I would like to,” “my studies and work are affected by my smartphone use”.
3. The third group includes questions connected with the emotional factor (emotional gains from smartphones) based on questions 10-18, 20, 25-26, 28 from the SAS questionnaire (items 23-29 in our questionnaire). For example, “When I am busy with my smartphone I am able to forget about my sorrows,” “I feel depressed and stressed when my smartphone is out of reach.”
4. The fourth group comprises questions that reflect pressure from the social environment as a factor in problematic smartphone use, with two of the items based on questions 34 and 35 in the SAS questionnaire (items 30-34 in our questionnaire). For example, “When people around me start to use their smartphones, I also do even if I don’t have a real need to do so,” and “I use my smartphone more than I would like, because of people around me.”
5. The fifth group is the authorized Hebrew translation (Etzion & Laski, 1998) of the standard full Big Five personality questionnaire (McCrae & John, 1992) that represents the personality factor in our study comprising 44 items that measure openness, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and neuroticism (items 35-78 in the questionnaire). The translated questionnaire was validated on a sample of 168 high school teachers in Israel (Etzion & Laski, 1998) and was found valid and internally reliable with $\alpha = 0.80$ for extroversion, $\alpha = 0.80$ for neuroticism, $\alpha = 0.68$ for agreeableness, $\alpha = 0.76$ for openness, and $\alpha = 0.73$ for conscientiousness.

6. Finally, in order to assess and compare the levels of different application usage and specific needs, we adapted Bergman's et al. (2012) methodology for creating two summarizing questions (items 79 and 80 on the questionnaire). This type of estimates was validated in (Bergman's et al., 2012) on a sample of 16 Israeli personal computer users by achieving a high significant Pearson correlation ($r=0.94$, $p<0.01$) between the actual subject's behavior percentage and the percentage estimated in the questionnaire, allowing for within-subject validation. We first asked the subjects to estimate their use of the various smartphone apps in percentages, with the total use of all mobile apps summing up to 100%. To determine which applications are the most prominent for smartphone users, we arranged a preliminary survey with about 50 subjects who were asked to provide the most popular smartphone application types they use. As a result, the final mobile app list included: (a) social networks (SNSs), (b) short text messages service (SMS), (c) informative apps, such as Wikipedia, Google searches, news and other informational sites, (d) WhatsApp, (e) Email, (f) e-commerce apps, (g) games, (h) the apps store and other apps (not mentioned above). The objective of the second summarizing question was to comparatively assess the main motivations for smartphone use. To this end, the subjects had to estimate the percentage of the effect of each of the different needs on the extent of their smartphone use, with the total use of all the needs summing up to 100%. The examined needs were collected from the reviewed literature and also derived from the user survey on smartphone apps above. They include: (a) the need for a virtual community (using social apps), (b) the emotional need (such as improving their mood and sense of security), (c) the need for information (Wikipedia, searches using search engines, news sites, etc.), (d) technology-triggered need - the need to check the content on the device as response to sound notification triggers (reminders, ringing and beeping), (e) the need to follow the social environment (pressure of people around the subject using their smartphones), (f) no reason or no defined need.

In item groups 2-5, the answers were measured according to the level of the respondents' agreement with the assertions on a 1-5 Likert scale, where 1 is defined as "a very low level of agreement" with a given assertion, 2 is a "low level of agreement", 3 is "an intermediate level of agreement", 4 represents "a high level of agreement" and 5 is "a very high level of agreement" with a given assertion.

The following factors' variables were defined:

1. Generation – calculated by dividing the subjects into three age groups, defining different generations (Barford & Hester, 2011; Johnston & Goldsmith, 2015): (a) Generation X, born before 1980, who grew up without information technologies and modern communications

devices, and were only exposed to them as adults; (b) Generation Y, born from 1980 to 1995, “the transient generation”, who were exposed to smartphones during adolescence but not in childhood, and (c) Generation Z, born between 1996 and 2003, “the mobile natives”, who were exposed to mobile phones and smartphones from their early childhood (McCrandle & Wolfinger, 2010). We chose to define Generation Z as high school students in Israel, since they were no older than 19 at the time of the survey.

2. The emotional factor (group 3 of the questionnaire) – to calculate this variable’s score, we calculated the average score for all the items in this group. Cronbach’s α coefficient of the variable was 0.85.
3. The social-environmental factor (group 4 of the questionnaire) – to calculate this variable, we calculated the average score for all the items in this group. Cronbach’s α coefficient of the variable was 0.72.
4. The personality factor – this group of items included five sub-groups, each representing a different type of personality (open, extrovert, agreeable, conscientious and neurotic). Therefore, each of the five different variables was calculated according to the average value of the items in each sub-group – one for each personality type. The Cronbach’s α coefficient for neurotic personality was 0.82, for conscientiousness - 0.73, for openness - 0.74, for an extrovert personality it was 0.77, and for an agreeable personality it was 0.69.
5. The summarizing question for the extent of the use of the different apps was broken down into seven different variables, so that a separate variable was calculated for each app as a ranking score on a scale of 0-100.
6. The summarizing question on needs ranking (by percentages) was broken down into six different variables, so that each need was calculated as a ranking score on a scale of 0-100.

The dependent variable of the study was smartphone addictive behavior (SAB), constructed from the average scores of the item-group 2 above. Cronbach’s α coefficient for this variable was 0.90.

A test of internal consistency reliability (Cronbach’s α coefficient values) showed that the reliability of the defined above variables ranged between 0.69 and 0.90. We can conclude that the internal consistencies assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient are considered acceptable (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

2.3 Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed via Google forms at the beginning of 2015 among 216 respondents with different demographic backgrounds. The distribution took place using a mixed strategy aiming to reach a diversity of subjects from different age groups and generations. Particularly, we recruited

participants by posting a request with a link to the questionnaire on the authors' social networks, by publishing it on several popular Facebook group pages, as well as by direct email invitation addressed to students in Bar-Ilan University and to students of three high-schools in different districts of the country.

This study received ethical approval and was conducted in accordance with the American Psychology Association (APA) ethical requirements. Participants could complete the online survey anonymously from any personal computer. They were first presented with a title page of the questionnaire which stated that they are invited to anonymously contribute to an academic research by anonymously participating in a survey on smartphone usage behavior, and in case of consent, they could move forward to the next page to start answering the questionnaire. It was also made clear that no personal information will be collected by the researchers and their responses will be used solely for the purposes of the study. The IRB of the Faculty of Humanities at Bar-Ilan University approved the experiment.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Analysis of the results was conducted using standard statistical tools. Pearson-correlations between all the research variables were calculated to reveal their inter-relationships and, particularly, to determine various factors strongly related to SAB. ANOVA tests were applied to examine the differences between the three generations for the various research variables. Finally, we constructed multi-variate linear regression models to predict SAB for the entire sample, and for the various generations separately. We further analyze and discuss the differences between these models.

3. Results

In this section we present the results of the statistical analysis, conducted to address the research hypothesis presented in the Introduction. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis and Pearson correlations for the various research variables are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the mean addictive behavior level was moderate – 2.7 out of 5. Although around 6% of the sample population received a mean score of 4 or above (high or very high) out of 5, according to our addictive behavior scale. Likewise, the WhatsApp and social network applications were prominent among the mobile apps uses. Games use was relatively low and not so dominant. The need for a virtual community (37%) and the need for information (20%) were the most prominent among the various needs leading to smartphone use.

To examine the correlation between the various factors and smartphone addictive behavior level, we computed two-tailed Pearson correlations. A strong significant positive correlation can be seen between addictive smartphone use and the social-environmental, emotional factors and 'daily smartphone usage in hours' variables. Table 2 shows that the factor with the highest correlation among the mobile apps is SNSs (and not WhatsApp or games). The strong positive correlation of SAB with neuroticism can be explained by this trait characterizing individuals who tend to be more influenced by society. There is also a significant negative correlation between conscientious personality and smartphone addictive behavior. It was also found that there was a significant negative correlation between age and the emotional factor (-0.26), and age and the social-environmental factor (-0.35). This means that younger people experience greater emotional dependence on smartphone, and are more influenced by the environment regarding smartphone use than older smartphone users.

Table 2: Means, standard deviations, and two-tailed Pearson correlations for all research variables over the entire sample, N=209. Cronbach alphas appear in the diagonal.

		M e a n	S T D	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
1	SAB	2.71	0.76	.90																							
2	Emotional factor	2.65	0.83	.72	.85																						
3	Social factor	2.94	0.84	.76	.70	.72																					
4	Extroversion	3.29	0.70	-.03	-.08	.02	.77																				
5	Neuroticism	2.86	0.79	.37	.22	.26	-.19	.82																			
6	Aggreableness	3.76	0.57	-.21	-.14	-.09	.10	-.37	.69																		
7	Conscientious	3.59	0.60	-.24	-.21	-.27	.27	-.33	-.29	.73																	
8	Openness	3.73	0.63	-.05	-.05	.01	.29	-.05	.04	.13	.74																
9	Age	28.34	11.04	-.18	-.26	-.35	.05	-.17	.04	.15	.07	-															
10	Time of usage	4.03	2.08	.09	.01	-.05	-.04	-.09	.00	.13	.00	.27	-														
11	Daily usage	6.07	4.55	.48	.40	.36	-.04	.14	-.01	.12	-.04	.14	-.17	-													
12	SNSs	22.71	16.52	.30	.22	.42	.11	.17	.05	-.18	.03	-.19	.05	.10	-												
13	SMS	7.40	8.48	-.09	-.07	-.10	.14	.03	-.12	.05	.04	.20	-.15	-.14	-.19	-											
14	Games	6.65	9.62	.04	-.14	-.03	.11	.00	.13	.09	.05	.13	-.06	.05	-.14	-.02	-										
15	WhatsApp	31.75	16.06	.05	-.02	.06	-.02	.04	.05	.08	.16	.33	.03	.14	-.25	-.27	.11	-									
16	Information app	11.66	9.46	-.17	-.15	-.25	.02	.15	.05	.22	.13	.32	.14	-.19	-.17	-.02	-.18	-.34	-								
18	Email	9.45	9.23	-.12	-.16	-.25	.08	.08	.05	.19	.04	.44	.13	-.11	-.33	.02	-.24	-.25	.25	.04	-						
19	E-commerce	1.13	2.66	.03	.02	.00	.00	.06	-.04	.06	.00	.24	.06	.06	-.04	.00	.03	.04	.04	.10	.10	-					
20	Virtual community	36.83	21.54	.01	-.01	.10	.02	.02	.10	.03	.11	.17	.05	.06	.09	.15	.10	.39	.21	.02	.15	.15	-				
21	Emotional need	9.26	11.47	.13	.30	.11	-.18	.23	.01	-.16	.06	.14	.08	.11	.12	-.04	.08	.09	.09	.17	.14	.03	.04	-			
22	Information need	20.27	18.04	-.18	-.20	-.24	.10	.07	-.10	.18	.11	.29	.10	.18	.06	.16	.03	.30	.46	.01	.20	.10	.24	.22	-		
23	Environment need	5.42	5.90	.32	.33	.40	.00	.06	-.04	.11	.07	.12	.04	.22	.18	.09	.06	.14	.14	.04	.07	.06	.09	.02	.17	-	
24	Tech-trigger need	12.23	15.41	.13	.19	.20	.09	.00	.06	.07	.00	.18	.00	.11	.11	.13	.11	.03	.07	.00	.25	.01	.33	.13	.16	.01	-
25	Without reason	7.46	10.33	.23	.20	.26	.08	.05	-.03	.01	.06	.13	.11	.11	.09	.02	.01	.11	.17	.04	.09	.02	.19	.06	.19	.35	.00

Note: All correlations in this table greater in magnitude than .21 are statistically significant at $p < .05$ after Bonferroni correction.

To investigate whether there are differences between addictive behavior level and factors related to this behavior among different generations, we performed the one-way ANOVA tests. This is to examine the differences between the three generations for the various research variables. Table 3 presents the results of these tests. It can be seen that there are significant differences between the generations in their addictive behavior level, so that Generation Y (the middle generation) has the highest addictive behavior rate, followed by Generation Z, and Generation X has the lowest addictive behavior level. Regarding the emotional and social-environmental factors, their levels were significantly higher among subjects from Generation Z, as compared to the two older generations. The test also showed significant difference between the generations for the time of smartphone use in years, $F(2,207)=4.82$, $p=0.040$, so that Generation Z (the youngest generation) had a shorter time of usage than the two older generations. It is interesting to note that for a univariate analysis of variance, when controlling the variable of time of usage in years, the difference in addictive behavior between the generations is still significant: $F(2, 207)=4.6$, $p=0.001$. Interestingly, no difference was found between the generations regarding daily usage, meaning that the younger generation that has its usage limited in educational frameworks still has the same daily smartphone usage time as adults. In addition, we can see from Table 3 that younger people make significantly more use of social networks (with an advantage to Generation Y), and WhatsApp (with an advantage to Generation Z), whereas the older generation (Generation X) use significantly more email, informative mobile apps, and SMS text messages.

Table 3: Differences between generations in the various research variables according to the one-way ANOVA analysis.

Variables by generation		N	Mean	SD	F	Sig (<i>p</i>)
SAB	X	48	2.41	0.71	5.145**	.007
	Y	90	2.83	0.70		
	Z	71	2.74	0.83		
	Total	209	2.71	0.76		
Time of usage in years	X	48	4.47	2.50	4.820*	.040
	Y	90	4.28	1.98		
	Z	71	3.42	1.76		
	Total	209	4.03	2.08		
Daily usage in hours	X	48	5.29	5.24	1.272	.283
	Y	90	6.02	4.43		
	Z	71	6.64	4.15		

	Total	209	6.07	4.55		
Emotional factor	X	48	2.38	0.80	6.372**	.002
	Y	90	2.60	0.74		
	Z	71	2.90	0.89		
	Total	209	2.65	0.83		
Social environmental factor	X	48	2.51	0.85	11.698**	.000
	Y	90	2.94	0.71		
	Z	71	3.23	0.88		
	Total	209	2.94	0.84		
Cross-generational Differences in Application usage						
SNSs usage	X	48	15.78	15.39	5.993**	.003
	Y	90	25.32	16.01		
	Z	71	24.16	16.80		
	Total	209	22.71	16.52		
SMS usage	X	48	11.90	12.67	9.448**	.000
	Y	90	6.02	5.98		
	Z	71	6.13	6.57		
	Total	209	7.40	8.48		
Games	X	48	6.22	12.14	1.454	.236
	Y	90	5.66	8.29		
	Z	71	8.20	9.18		
	Total	209	6.65	9.62		
WhatsApp use	X	48	23.66	14.91	14.422**	.000
	Y	90	30.43	14.13		
	Z	71	39.01	17.98		
	Total	209	31.75	16.67		
Informational applications usage	X	48	14.60	11.23	8.845**	.000
	Y	90	12.88	9.29		
	Z	71	8.07	7.09		
	Total	209	11.66	9.46		
Application store use	X	48	4.18	3.98	0.127	.881
	Y	90	3.90	6.25		
	Z	71	4.31	4.66		
	Total	209	4.10	5.26		
Email use	X	48	15.01	11.38	27.899**	.000

	Y	90	10.73	8.54		
	Z	71	3.99	4.35		
	Total	209	9.45	9.23		
E-commerce	X	48	1.26	2.27	1.462	.297
	Y	90	0.78	1.84		
	Z	71	1.48	3.60		
	Total	209	1.13	2.66		
Cross-generational differences in needs for using smartphones						
Need for virtual community	X	48	30.49	18.77	3.486*	.032
	Y	90	37.07	21.35		
	Z	71	40.92	22.78		
	Total	209	36.83	21.54		
Need for emotional support	X	48	7.49	11.86	1.890	.154
	Y	90	8.60	11.48		
	Z	71	11.32	11.03		
	Total	209	9.26	11.47		
Need for information	X	48	25.53	19.83	10.425**	.000
	Y	90	23.31	19.30		
	Z	71	12.73	11.80		
	Total	209	20.27	18.04		
Environmental influence	X	48	4.88	6.49	1.422	.244
	Y	90	4.96	5.47		
	Z	71	6.37	5.97		
	Total	209	5.42	5.90		
Technology-triggered need	X	48	16.71	19.29	3.298*	.039
	Y	90	11.96	16.48		
	Z	71	9.47	9.27		
	Total	209	12.23	15.41		
Without specific reason or goal	X	48	5.88	8.35	1.711	.183
	Y	90	6.95	8.75		
	Z	71	9.20	12.99		
	Total	209	7.46	10.33		

*p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Based on the above findings, we built hierarchical regression models for the entire sample, as well as for each generation in isolation. All the regression models were significant, as can be seen from Table 4, with the predictive variables adding between 69%-79% to the explained variance of the dependent variable – the smartphone addictive behavior. We can see that the variables shared by all the generations and the entire sample that contributed the most to the explained variance, are the social-environmental and emotional factors. For the whole sample, the unique factor was the generation. As we saw above, Generation Y reported higher addictive behavior levels than the other generations. The unique factors common to Generation Y and Generation Z were neurotic personality and daily smartphone usage in hours (they did not affect the Generation X respondents). Thus, more intensive daily use of smartphone might cause higher addictive behavior in younger users. The only unique variable for Generation Z is the use of the WhatsApp application that was not significant for the older generations. This finding was also supported by the amount this application was used among the youngest generation which was significantly higher than among the older generations. It is interesting to note that social networks and games were not found to be a significantly influencing factor for any of the generations.

Table 4: Hierarchical multi-variate regression coefficients for significant factors to predict addictive behavior level for the entire sample and for the three generations.

Beta coefficients for SAB (smartphone addictive behavior) as a dependent variable for different samples				
Predictors	All sample, N=209	Gen. X, N=48	Gen. Y, N=90	Gen. Z, N=71
Social-environmental factor	.458*(.000)	0.480*(.001)	.458*(.000)	.422*(.000)
Emotional factor	.328*(.000)	0.420*(.002)	.354*(.000)	.392*(.000)
Daily usage in hours	.172*(.000)	.145(.117)	.178*(.003)	.121*(.041)
Big 5 Neuroticism	.164*(.000)	.105(.210)	.202*(.006)	.176*(.003)
Big 5 Agreeableness	-.077(.055)	-.128(.130)	-.078(.256)	.022(.736)
Smartphone usage in years	.069(.073)	.038(.651)	.111(.110)	.143*(.017)
SNSs	-.012(.776)	-.134(.138)	.022(.746)	.121(.089)
WhatsApp usage	.006(.138)	.061(.474)	-.039(.539)	.209*(.002)
Information apps	.001(.974)	.004(.960)	-.033(.616)	.024(.702)
Without specific reason	.048(.213)	.049(.563)	.013(.833)	.004(.956)

Generation X vs. Y and Z	.213*(.000)	-	-	-
Generation Y vs. X and Z	.113*(.003)	-	-	-
R²	0.73	0.71	0.69	0.79
F	F(6,202)=89.65 (.000)	F(2,45)=52.74 (.000)	F(4,87)=45.34 (.000)	F(6,68)=37.33 (.000)

Corresponding *p* values appear in parenthesis. Generational variables exist only for the entire sample model. Significant factors are marked with asterisk (*).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

The goal of this study was to examine cross-generational differences in smartphone users' addictive behavior. The effect of age on tendency to smartphone addiction was examined in a recent study in Netherlands (van Deursen et al., 2015), and a significant negative correlation was found between the variables. However, in the current study, we aimed to further examine the differences between groups of subjects divided by generation. Therefore, the first major finding of this study, which as far as we know has not been directly addressed in the previous work, is that there are significant differences between the generations in the smartphone addictive behavior.

Interestingly, we found that it was actually Generation Y, the middle generation that received significantly greater addictive behavior scores than the other two generations. Hence, hypothesis H5a was supported, while H5b was rejected by our findings. The implication of this result is that the effect of age on addictive behavior is non-linear. We suggest the following reasons to explain this finding:

- a. The transition from a situation of lack or limited availability of the mobile technology to its high availability, is what caused over-use and addictive behavior for Generation Y. This is similar to the known phenomenon of eating disorders, where a very restrictive diet leads to binge eating and bulimic episodes (Tuschl, 1990). In contrast, users who grew up with an unlimited access to mobile and smartphone technology from birth (as Generation Z's subjects did) is capable of a healthier psychological reaction to it. Probably, since these users see this technology as a natural element of their life, and thus less tend to develop the addictive behavior.
- b. Generation X did not grow up with the mobile technology, but since its members were exposed to it as adults with a relatively stable personality (as opposed to Generation Y who were exposed to technology during adolescence), they are less connected with it and adopted to it (Charness & Bosman, 1992; Lenhart et al., 2010). They also use new apps less, particularly social apps, make more informative use of their smartphones, as shown in the

Results section above, are less influenced by the environment, and therefore are less likely to become addicted to this technology.

In addition, the research findings indicate the technological transition over the generations – from using email and SMS text messages, that has the highest use level for Generation X, to use of social networks that is most popular among Generation Y, and to WhatsApp that is the most widely used among Generation Z. Thus, our H5d hypothesis that social applications will be used more by younger generations is only partly supported by the findings, as email and SMS, which are also considered as social applications, were used more by Generation X than by the younger generations. These cross-generational differences revealed in this study indicate the target populations and point to the most optimal communication technologies of approaching them. In particular, this can be useful for advertising and marketing campaigns, as well as publicity campaigns to improve public psychological well-being aimed at preventing smartphone addiction. In addition, the dominance of WhatsApp and social network usage for the young generations might indicate the effectiveness of the social platform for M-learning.

Regarding the various factors of addictive behavior, there was no significant correlation between smartphone addictive behavior and technology-triggered need, which rejects the H1 hypothesis of the research. It was found that social environment is the strongest factor related to addictive behavior thus supporting the H2 research hypothesis. This finding supports those of previous studies that subjects more influenced by social pressure in general have a tendency towards more smartphone addiction (Chiu, 2014; Samaha & Hawi, 2016; Sapacz et al., 2016). However, this study focused on examining social pressure for smartphone use, and not social or psychological pressure in the subject's life in general. H5C was also supported by our findings since social environment factor was significantly higher for generation Z than for Y and X.

The second-ranked factor – that is common to and significant for all generations – is the emotional gain from smartphones, indicating that emotional gratifications from smartphone use are related with increasing the addictive behavior. The emotional gain was found as one of the most important factors of smartphone addictive behavior for all the generations. This result validates the H3 hypothesis. The youngest generation experiences the highest emotional gain from the smartphone use compared to the older generations. Nevertheless, for generation X emotional gain was also one of the two most significant factors in the multi-variate regression model. Another intriguing variable highly correlated with addiction was use of smartphones “without specific reason” – the more smartphone use is without a reason, the greater the tendency to addiction. This variable might be also related to the emotional gain, such as boredom or sadness relief, which is not perceived by users' as a specific

rationally interpreted need, and yet has is related to their smartphone usage behavior. Smartphone use might help relieve an individual's negative emotions and moods and increase fun and self-confidence. This emotional gain motivates users to use their smartphones more excessively and habitually, without specific rational need and with less self-regulation and control, which might eventually lead to addictive behavior as shown in (van Deursen et al., 2015).

Use of the social networks and the need for a virtual community have a high significant correlation with SAB in accordance with previous studies (Salehan & Negahban, 2013; Jeong, Kim, Yum, & Hwang, 2016; van Deursen et al., 2015), thus positively addressing the research question R1. Yet, they were not found as a significant factor in the computed regression model. In addition, our findings show that informational mobile apps and the need for information were negatively correlated with smartphone addictive behavior, but the correlation was not significant. In contrast to the previous study (Jeong et al., 2016), games were not found to be factors of SAB and were used relatively little by all the generations. The daily usage time was found as a positive predictive factor of addictive behavior for the two younger generations, which supports the previous findings that excessive and habitual use might lead to smartphone addiction (van Deursen et al., 2015; Oulasvirta et al., 2012). Relatively little use of apps stores and e-commerce shows that companies interested in attracting buyers using smartphones seemingly need to develop better smartphone interfaces, and invest more effort in advertising in the social apps.

Our findings reinforce those of the previous study that neuroticism contributes to smartphone addiction (Pearson & Hussein, 2015), but only among the younger generations. Interestingly, there was a significant negative relationship between conscientiousness and SAB. This provides a positive answer to research question R2.

Unlike previous studies (Lee, Chang, Lin, & Cheng, 2014; Park & Lee, 2014; van Deursen et al., 2015), we did not find significant differences in smartphone addictive behavior between men and women thus rejecting the H4 research hypothesis. These findings might indicate cultural differences between the population in Israel and that of the countries, where the above studies were carried out.

All these findings lead us to the conclusion that the content, information, and technological triggers are less significant and addictive to the users, but the behavior of people around the user and the pressure their behavior exerts toward smartphone use, as well as emotional gains (that are also mainly derived from social use) are the most addictive factors in the case of smartphones. As mentioned in the Introduction previous research described many harmful outcomes of SAB, such as, physical, psychological, economic and social problems, lower work effectiveness, learning and concentration.

Awareness of the factors of SAB for each generation found in this study might help avoid these negative effects and improve public health and well-being.

Interestingly, the only application found as a predictive factor that significantly contributes to the regression model for addictive behavior (only among the Generation Z) was WhatsApp. The meaning of this finding is that this application might have a certain characteristic, not found in other social applications examined in the current study (such as SNSs and SMS text messages). The reasons for this strong influence of WhatsApp on addictive behavior of young smartphone users are subject for further research.

5. Study Limitations

The limitation of the study is that it is based on a convenience sample of participants recruited mostly from social networks and educational institutions. Hence, the subjects' self-reporting could be biased (Landers and Behrend, 2015), particularly in studies of problematic behavior, and produce answers that are seen as socially desirable (Matthews, Roberts, & Zeidner, 2004). Especially, the young subjects from Generation Z might have poorer self-awareness (Brinthaup & Lipka, 1992, p. 138), and therefore their self-reporting might be less reliable than that of the adults. In addition, several variables tested in this research were based on single-item measures and thus can have significant reliability and validity limitations. Furthermore, the proposed SAB measure might not fully capture and represent the different characteristics of the smartphone addictive behavior. The user perception of the measure's items and their representativeness as problematic or addictive might differ among different generations and change over time, leading to theoretical complications. Therefore, qualitative scales for examining behavioral addiction are to be developed, in addition to the quantitative models suggested in the literature and in the current study. Likewise, there was a different, and not entirely balanced, number of subjects from each generation, that possibly influenced the correlations and the regression model for the entire sample. The recruitment process based on volunteers might also impose some limitation on representativeness of the study sample, as they might differ in their attitudes from other users in their social group (van Deursen et al., 2015), or in our case, generation. The study respondents were all Israeli citizens, thus the findings might reflect cultural, social and technological characteristics of the Israeli population.

Finally, although the findings of this study reflect the behavior of different generations in Israel, nowadays media spans national borders, and events that define generational consciousness are transmitted by the Internet, thereby creating global generations (Edmunds & Turner, 2014). Therefore, further research might apply the proposed methodology on subjects from other countries and compare

their findings on cross-generational differences in smartphone addictive behavior to those of the current study.

Appendix A

The Measures

A.1 Smartphone addictive behavior scale	
1	My studies/work are affected by my smartphone use
2	It is difficult for me not to use my smartphone even during a lecture, staff meeting, meeting with other people, or conversation with a friend
3	I suffer from pain in my neck, wrist, shoulders, headaches, dizziness, and dry eyes, after using my smartphone
4	I also use my smartphone late at night and before going to bed, and even when I should be sleeping
5	My smartphone use is an important part of my life
6	People who are close to me complain that I neglect them because of my “exaggerated” use of my smartphone
7	Sometimes I imagine I can hear my smartphone
8	It would be hard for me not to have my smartphone
9	I think about my smartphone even when it isn’t within reach
10	I get irritated when people disturb me when I am in the middle of surfing or using an app
11	I take my smartphone with me everywhere, even to the bathroom, even if I am in a hurry to get there
12	When I go to sleep, my smartphone is usually next to me
13	My smartphone use prevents me from participating in social activities
14	I am constantly checking to see if I have notifications or updates, even if I didn’t get a warning about it
15	I am busy with my smartphone for more time than I would like to
16	Immediately after finishing using my smartphone, I have an urgent need to use it again
17	I have unsuccessfully tried to limit the time I spend with my smartphone
18	Sometimes, I initiate using my smartphone to avoid communicating or interacting with the people around me
A.2 Emotional gain scale	

1	I enjoy my smartphone
2	My smartphone makes me feel calm and self-confident
3	When I am busy with my smartphone I am able to forget about my sorrows
4	I look at my smartphone when I am irritated, so that I won't have to deal with what is bothering me
5	I use my smartphone to relieve boredom, irritability, anger, loneliness, or sadness
6	I think my life would be boring and lacking fun without my smartphone
7	I feel depressed and stressed when my smartphone is out of reach

A.3 Social-environmental scale

1	My main use for my smartphone is for social apps which I use to get to know new friends
2	I check updates on social networks like Facebook and Twitter as soon as I wake up
3	Most of my communication with my friends and relatives is through my smartphone
4	When people around me start to use their smartphones, I also always do so, even if I don't have an actual reason for this
5	I use my smartphone more than I really need to or want to because of the people around me

References

- Aboujaoude, E., Koran, L. M., Gamel, N., Large, M. D., & Serpe, R. T. (2006). Potential markers for problematic Internet use: a telephone survey of 2,513 adults. *CNS spectrums, 11*(10), 750-755.
- Amichai-Hamburger, Y., Wainapel, G., & Fox, S. (2002). "On the Internet no one knows I'm an introvert": Extroversion, neuroticism, and Internet interaction. *CyberPsychology & Behavior, 5*(2), 125-128.
- Barford, I. N., & Hester, P. T. (2011). Analysis of generation Y workforce motivation using multiattribute utility theory. *Defense Acquisition Research Journal, 18*(1), 63-80.
- Beranuy, M., Oberst, U., Carbonell, X., & Chamarro, A. (2009). Problematic Internet and mobile phone use and clinical symptoms in college students: The role of emotional intelligence. *Computers in human behavior, 25*(5), 1182-1187.
- Bergman, O., Beyth-Marom, R., Nachmias, R., Gradovitch, N., & Whittaker, S. (2008). Improved search engines and navigation preference in personal information management. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems, 26* (4), 1-24. doi: 10.1145/1402256.1402259.
- Bernroider, E. W., Krumay, B., & Margiol, S. (2014). *Not Without My Smartphone! Impacts of Smartphone Addiction on Smartphone Usage*. Paper presented at the 25th Australasian Conference on Information Systems, Auckland.

- Bianchi, A., & Phillips, J. G. (2005). Psychological predictors of problem mobile phone use. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 8(1), 39-51.
- Billieux, J., & Van der Linden, M. (2012). Problematic use of the Internet and self-regulation: a review of the initial studies. *The Open Addiction Journal*, 5, 24-29.
- Billieux, J., Maurage, P., Lopez-Fernandez, O., Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2015). Can disordered mobile phone use be considered a behavioral addiction? An update on current evidence and a comprehensive model for future research. *Current Addiction Reports*, 2(2), 156-162.
- Brinthaupt, T. M., & Lipka, R. P. (Eds.). (1992). *The self: Definitional and methodological issues*. New York: SUNY Press.
- Carbonell, X., Oberst, U., & Beranuy, M. (2013). The cell phone in the twenty-first century: A risk for addiction or a necessary tool? In P. Miller (Ed.), *Principles of addiction: Comprehensive addictive behaviors and disorders, Vol. 1* (pp.901–909). San Diego, CA: Academic Press. <http://doi.org/3h2>
- Charness, N., & Bosman, E.A. (1992). Human factors and age. In: Craik, F.I.M., & Salthouse, T.A. (Eds.), *The handbook of aging and cognition* (pp. 495-551). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Chiu, S. I. (2014). The relationship between life stress and smartphone addiction on Taiwanese university student: A mediation model of learning self-Efficacy and social self-Efficacy. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 34, 49-57.
- Choi, K., Son, H., Park, M., Han, J., Kim, K., Lee, B., & Gwak, H. (2009). Internet overuse and excessive daytime sleepiness in adolescents. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*, 63(4), 455-462.
- Chou, C., & Hsiao, M. C. (2000). Internet addiction, usage, gratification, and pleasure experience: the Taiwan college students' case. *Computers & Education*, 35(1), 65-80.
- Clarke, A. T. (2006). Coping with interpersonal stress and psychosocial health among children and adolescents: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 35(1), 10-23.
- Edmunds, J., & Turner, B. S. (2005). Global generations: social change in the twentieth century. *The British journal of sociology*, 56(4), 559-577.
- Etzion D., & Laski, S. (1998). Hebrew Version of the Big Five Index by Permission. Tel Aviv University, Faculty of management, the Institute of Business Research. <https://www.ocf.berkeley.edu/~johnlab/pdfs/BFI-Hebrew.pdf>, last retrieved May 5th 2016.
- Finn, S. (1992). Television “addiction?” An evaluation of four competing media-use models. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 69(2), 422-435.
- Frangos, C. C., Frangos, K. C., & Kiohos, A. (2010). Internet addiction among Greek university students: Demographic associations with the phenomenon, using the Greek version of Young's Internet Addiction Test. *International Journal of Economic Sciences and Applied Research*, 3(1), 49-74.

- Greenberg, J. L., Lewis, S. E., & Dodd, D. K. (1999). Overlapping addictions and self-esteem among college men and women. *Addictive behaviors, 24*(4), 565-571.
- Griffiths, M. D., & Hunt, N. (1998). Dependence on computer games by adolescents. *Psychological reports, 82*(2), 475-480.
- Hong, F. Y., Chiu, S. I., & Huang, D. H. (2012). A model of the relationship between psychological characteristics, mobile phone addiction and use of mobile phones by Taiwanese university female students. *Computers in Human Behavior, 28*(6), 2152-2159.
- Howe, N., & Strauss, W. (2004). *Millennials rising: The next great generation*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Huisman, A., Garretsen, H. F. L., & Van Den Eijnden, R. J. J. M. (2000). Problematisch Internetgebruik: een pilot study in Rotterdam. *IVO, Instituut voor Onderzoek naar Leefwijzen & Verslaving*.
- Jenaro, C., Flores, N., Gómez-Vela, M., González-Gil, F., & Caballo, C. (2007). Problematic internet and cell-phone use: Psychological, behavioral, and health correlates. *Addiction research & theory, 15*(3), 309-320.
- Jeong, S. H., Kim, H., Yum, J. Y., & Hwang, Y. (2016). What type of content are smartphone users addicted to?: SNS vs. games. *Computers in Human Behavior, 54*, 10-17.
- McCrae, R. R., & John, O. P. (1992). An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications. *Journal of personality, 60*(2), 175-215.
- Kardefelt-Winther, D. (2014). A conceptual and methodological critique of internet addiction research: Towards a model of compensatory internet use. *Computers in Human Behavior, 31*, 351-354.
- Kwon, M., Lee, J. Y., Won, W. Y., Park, J. W., Min, J. A., Hahn, C., & Kim, D. J. (2013). Development and validation of a smartphone addiction scale (SAS). *PloS ONE, 8*(2), e56936.
- Lanaj, K., Johnson, R. E., & Barnes, C. M. (2014). Beginning the workday yet already depleted? Consequences of late-night smartphone use and sleep. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 124*(1), 11-23.
- Landers, R.N., & Behrend, T.S (2015). An inconvenient truth: arbitrary distinctions between organizational, Mechanical Turk, and other convenience samples. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology, 8*, pp 142-164. doi:10.1017/iop.2015.13.
- LaRose, R., Lin, C. A., & Eastin, M. S. (2003). Unregulated Internet usage: Addiction, habit, or deficient self-regulation? *Media Psychology, 5*(3), 225-253.
- Lee, Y. K., Chang, C. T., Cheng, Z. H., & Lin, Y. (2015). Helpful-stressful cycle? Psychological links between type of mobile phone user and stress. *Behaviour & Information Technology, 35*(1), 75-86.
- Lee, Y. K., Chang, C. T., Lin, Y., & Cheng, Z. H. (2014). The dark side of smartphone usage: Psychological traits, compulsive behavior and technostress. *Computers in Human Behavior, 31*, 373-383.
- Lenhart, A., Purcell, K., Smith, A., & Zickuhr, K. (2010). Social media & mobile internet use among teens and young adults. *Pew Internet & American Life Project*. retrieved from

http://www.pewinternet.org/files/old-media/Files/Reports/2010/PIP_Social_Media_and_Young_Adults_Report_Final_with_toplines.pdf

- Li, S. M., & Chung, T. M. (2006). Internet function and Internet addictive behavior. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 22(6), 1067-1071.
- Lopez-Fernandez, O., Honrubia-Serrano, L., Freixa-Blanxart, M., & Gibson, W. (2014). Prevalence of problematic mobile phone use in British adolescents. *CyberPsychology, Behavior, and social networking*, 17(2), 91-98.
- Marlatt, G. A., Baer, J. S., Donovan, D. M., & Kivlahan, D. R. (1988). Addictive behaviors: Etiology and treatment. *Annual review of Psychology*, 39(1), 223-252.
- Matthews, G., Roberts, R. D., & Zeidner, M. (2004). Seven myths about emotional intelligence. *Psychological Inquiry*, 15(3), 179-196.
- McIlwraith, R. D. (1998). "I'm addicted to television": The personality, imagination, and TV watching patterns of self-identified TV addicts. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 42(3), 371-386.
- McCordle, M., & Wolfinger, E. (2010). Generations defined. *Ethos*, 18(1), 8.
- Oulasvirta, A., Rattenbury, T., Ma, L., & Raita, E. (2012). Habits make smartphone use more pervasive. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 16(1), 105-114.
- Öztunç, M. (2013). Analysis of problematic mobile phone use, feelings of shyness and loneliness in accordance with several variables. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 106, 456-466.
- Park, N. and Lee, H. (2013). Nature of Youth Smartphone Addiction in Korea: Diverse Dimensions of Smartphone Use and Individual Traits, *Journal of Communication Research*, 51 (1), 100-132.
- Parker, J. D., Taylor, R. N., Eastabrook, J. M., Schell, S. L., & Wood, L. M. (2008). Problem gambling in adolescence: Relationships with internet misuse, gaming abuse and emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 45(2), 174-180.
- Pearson, C., & Hussain, Z. (2015). Smartphone use, addiction, narcissism, and personality: a mixed methods investigation. *International Journal of Cyber Behavior, Psychology and Learning (IJCBPL)*, 5(1), 17-32.
- Queitzsch, S. (2015). Five generation juggle. *Johnston & Goldsmith, Think Paper*. Retrieved from [http://www.johnstongoldsmith.com.au/ThinkPapers/JG_Thinkpaper2%20\(1\).pdf](http://www.johnstongoldsmith.com.au/ThinkPapers/JG_Thinkpaper2%20(1).pdf)
- Rozin, P., & Stoess, C. (1993). Is there a general tendency to become addicted? *Addictive Behaviors*, 18(1), 81-87.
- Salehan, M., & Negahban, A. (2013). Social networking on smartphones: When mobile phones become addictive. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(6), 2632-2639.
- Samaha, M., & Hawi, N. S. (2016). Relationships among smartphone addiction, stress, academic performance, and satisfaction with life. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 57, 321-325.

- Sapacz, M., Rockman, G., & Clark, J. (2016). Are we addicted to our cell phones? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 57, 153-159.
- Shaffer, H. J. (1996). Understanding the means and objects of addiction: Technology, the internet, and gambling. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 12(4), 461-469.
- Smith, R. (1986). Television addiction. In J. Bryant & D. Zillmann (Eds.), *Perspectives on media effects* (pp.109-128). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Song, I., Larose, R., Eastin, M. S., & Lin, C. A. (2004). Internet gratifications and Internet addiction: On the uses and abuses of new media. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 7(4), 384-394.
- Tan, Ç., Pamuk, M., & Dönder, A. (2013). Loneliness and mobile phone. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 103, 606-611.
- Tang, J. H., Chen, M. C., Yang, C. Y., Chung, T. Y., & Lee, Y. A. (2016). Personality traits, interpersonal relationships, online social support, and Facebook addiction. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(1), 102-108.
- Tuschl, R. J. (1990). From dietary restraint to binge eating: some theoretical considerations. *Appetite*, 14(2), 105-109.
- Van Deursen, A. J., Bolle, C. L., Hegner, S. M., & Kommers, P. A. (2015). Modeling habitual and addictive smartphone behavior: The role of smartphone usage types, emotional intelligence, social stress, self-regulation, age, and gender. *Computers in human behavior*, 45, 411-420.
- Weinstein, A., & Lejoyeux, M. (2010). Internet addiction or excessive internet use. *The American journal of drug and alcohol abuse*, 36(5), 277-283.
- Whang, L. S. M., Lee, S., & Chang, G. (2003). Internet over-users' psychological profiles: a behavior sampling analysis on Internet addiction. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 6(2), 143-150.
- Yang, S. C., & Tung, C. J. (2007). Comparison of Internet addicts and non-addicts in Taiwanese high school. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 23(1), 79-96.
- Young, K. S. (1998). Internet addiction: The emergence of a new clinical disorder. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 1(3), 237-244.
- Young, K. S. (1999). Internet addiction: symptoms, evaluation and treatment. In L. Van de Creek, & X. Jackson, *Innovations in clinical practice: a source book* (Vol. 17; 19-31). Sarasota, FL: Professional Resource Press.
- Young, K., & Abreu, C. (2011). Internet addiction. A handbook and guide to evaluation and treatment. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Yu, J. J., Kim, H., & Hay, I. (2013). Understanding adolescents' problematic Internet use from a social/cognitive and addiction research framework. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(6), 2682-2689.